

Experimental Study on Use of Fly Ash in Concrete

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Abstract: *This study investigates the reviews on use of Class F fly ash as a partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) in concrete, focusing on its effects on mechanical properties and durability. The research aims to identify the optimal fly ash content that enhances performance while maintaining workability. By incorporating fly ash, a byproduct of coal combustion, the study also addresses waste management and sustainability concerns, potentially reducing the carbon footprint of concrete production. In conclusion, the use of fly ash in concrete is a promising strategy for sustainable construction, offering both environmental and economic benefits. Future research should focus on optimizing mix designs, exploring regional variations in fly ash properties, and developing guidelines for its effective use in diverse construction scenarios. By addressing these aspects, the adoption of fly ash in concrete can be further accelerated, contributing to greener construction practices.*

Keywords: *Class F fly ash, ordinary Portland cement (OPC), concrete, tensile strength, flexural strength, durability*

1. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is one of the largest consumers of natural resources and energy, contributing significantly to global carbon emissions. Concrete, the most widely used construction material, is primarily composed of cement, aggregates, and water. However, the production of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) is an energy-intensive process that releases a substantial amount of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. In light of growing environmental concerns and the push for sustainable development, researchers and engineers are increasingly exploring the use of industrial by-products as partial replacements for cement in concrete production.

Fly ash, a fine powdery residue generated from the combustion of pulverized coal in thermal power plants, is one such material that has shown considerable promise as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM). Rich in silica and alumina, fly ash exhibits pozzolanic properties that enhance the performance of concrete, particularly in terms of strength, workability, and durability. Its incorporation in concrete not only helps in reducing the environmental footprint of cement but also addresses the issue of fly ash disposal, which poses significant environmental and health risks.

This research paper presents an experimental study on the use of fly ash in concrete, aiming to evaluate its effects on the mechanical properties and overall performance of concrete mixes. By partially replacing cement with varying proportions of fly ash, this study seeks to determine the optimal percentage that can improve concrete quality without compromising its structural integrity. The findings of this research are expected to contribute to the advancement of sustainable construction practices by promoting the utilization of industrial waste in infrastructure development.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

More et al. (2024) presented Concrete mix of grade M30 to M70 with OPC mix without flyash compared with the HVFA mix which had 40% and 50% flyash replacement. The mechanical behaviour such as compressive strength in HVFA mix was less as compared with pure OPC mix on an average by 4 MPA also the rapid chloride penetration (RCPT) was found less than when compared with pure OPC mix for all grades of concrete. For M30 grade of concrete the RCPT values were 1412 coulomb which was less as compared with OPC mix, while the RCPT values with HVFA mix for M35, M40 M45, M50, M60 and M70 was 1412 coulomb, 1317 coulomb, 1056 coulomb, 1182 coulomb, 990 coulomb, 870 coulomb 991 coulomb respectively.

Tran et al. (2024) presented High-strength concrete (HSC) using supplementary cementitious material of 30% fly ash (FA) and various nano silica (NS) contents in this study. FA and NS are waste materials collected from local thermal plants and rice husk ash in Southern Vietnam, respectively. Different concentrations of NS at 0%, 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5% were incorporated into the base mixture in place of cement and FA. The water-to-binder ratio of 0.32 was constant for all the mixtures. Results indicated that the combination binder of cement, FA, and NS satisfied the setting time as pure cement binder. The slump test value was in the range of 30–40 mm by adjusting the superplasticizer. Mechanical properties of HSC were studied at various curing ages of 3, 7, 28, and 56 days, including compressive strength, flexural strength, elastic modulus, and abrasion resistance..

Thangavel et al. (2024) presented that Due to its better mechanical qualities and durability, stainless steel fibre reinforced concrete (SSFRC) is a form of composite material that is being utilised in construction more frequently. SSFRC is created by incorporating stainless steel fibres into a cement-based mixture, making it significantly stronger and less prone to corrosion and cracking than conventional concrete. An overview of the characteristics of SSFRC, such as its high tensile strength, ductility, and resistance to chemical and physical harm, is given in this abstract. The production procedure for SSFRC is also covered in this abstract, along with the crucial design factors that need to be taken into account when employing this material in construction projects. SSFRC is a desirable solution for a variety of applications due to its adaptability and durability.

Sajeevet al. (2024) presented the results of aresearch employing fly ash and red mud on functionally graded concrete. This uses M20gradeconcrete as regular concrete in the compression zone and M25 grade concrete in the tensionzone, where flyash and red mud substitute cement to different degrees (3%, 6%, 9%, 12%and15%, respectively).According to the results, the ideal proportion for a concrete beamis 12%redmudand 12% fly ash. Additionally, based on the load deflection curve, it is clear that functionallygraded concrete beams are stronger and more durable than regular concrete. Both the flyashandthe red mud functionally graded concrete were subjected to scanning electron microscopyexamination. It made it very evident which components had pores, which tend to make concrete stronger

Ghanim et al. (2023) presented the beneficial utilization of textile industry waste-derived pumice powder (PP) and its comparison with Fly Ash (FA)

in concrete. A total of ten mixes of concrete were prepared with PP, FA, and their ternary mixes (PF) by replacing cement with 15 %, 25 %, and 35 %, respectively. The results show that PP possesses higher pozzolanic potential attributed to the presence of higher content of amorphous silica (SiO₂) as detected in the X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) test and justified by the Strength Activity Index (SAI). Moreover, the addition of both pozzolana enhances rheological properties along with the workability of fresh concrete.

Karthigaet al. (2023) presented M₅₀ grade concrete was used for testing in which nearly 20% replacement of cement by weight using fly ash. Polypropylene fibres are used to enhance the strength and ductility aspects, aspect ratio was considered between 50 and 150. Mix design was done as per the IS codal provisions from which samples were prepared, with different proportions of concrete. Mechanical, durability and physical tests were conducted on the prepared samples. After the tests it was concluded that when 20% replacement of cement by fly ash and 3.5% of addition of fibres increased the compressive strength of concrete up to 68 N/mm².

Bajpaiet al. (2023) presented examines geopolymer concrete as interlocking paver blocks. Three concretes are compared: conventional cement, fly ash-geopolymer and fly ash–silica fume geopolymer. Sodium hydroxide solution is used in both geopolymer concretes, and sodium silicate solution is used in fly ash-based geopolymer concrete only. Rectangle and uni shape blocks are tested for compressive strength, flexural strength, abrasion resistance and freeze–thaw resistance. Dynamic drop loading test is conducted on block pavement with herringbone laying pattern . Results revealed that resistance to abrasion and water absorption of geopolymeris improved by adding silica fume . Freeze–thaw resistance is the lowest for cement concrete paver blocks. Lowest deflection occurred in block pavement of uni shape. Geopolymer concrete provides uniform load distribution than cement concrete. Cement concrete is slightly costlier than geopolymer concrete. This study concluded the geopolymer as suitable option for paver block applications.

Nguyenet al. (2023) presented the prediction model B4TW-SCC for the creep of self-compacting concrete (SCC), which still lacks accurate prediction models. Besides, the compressive creep of SCC was experimented with by partially replacing up to 40% of the cement weight with fly ash. The tested results indicated that fly ash is highly effective in decreasing the total and basic creep of SCC, corresponding to an increase in the contents of fly ash.

Chouguleet al. (2023) presented that When fly ash is added to concrete the amount of Portland cement may be reduced. Mix design of concrete with fly ash for high rise building and to study the consideration while designing a concrete mix of high grades. Now a day's use of fly ash as a partial replacement of cement is a common. And the demand is increasing day by day particularly for making high strength and highperformance concrete. Many researches done for the use of fly ash as a supplementary cementitious material. High volume fly ash concrete as a subject of current interest all over the world. Thermal power stations are left with an undesirable by-product, fly ash, in large quantities which is not able to effectively utilize or dispose of. The utilization of fly ash in concrete making to control the environmental pollution as well as it will be economical. Analysis of how compressive strength is affected due to with various proportions of cement & Fly ash in a concrete

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Material Selection and Preparation

The research follows an experimental approach to evaluate the effect of fly ash replacement in concrete on its mechanical and durability properties. The methodology consists of the following steps:

3.1.1 CEMENT

Ordinary Portland Cement, 43 Grade conforming to IS: 8112-1989. The results of the tests on cement sample are listed in Table 1.

Fig 3. 1 Ordinary Portland cement

Table 1 Test results for Ultratech 43 OPC

S.No.	Tests	Results
1	Normal consistency	29%
2	Initial Setting Time	85 Minutes
3	Final Setting Time	195 Minutes
4	Specific Gravity	3.10
5	7 days compressive strength of cement	41.2

		N/mm ²
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3.1.2 Coarse Aggregate

Aggregates are important constituents of concrete. They form integral structure to the concrete, reduce shrinkage, and affect economy. Aggregates occupy 70 to 80 percent of volume of the concrete. Properties such as crushing strength, durability, modulus of elasticity, maximum size, gradation, shape and surface texture characteristics, percentage of deleterious materials as well as flakiness and elongation indices need special consideration while selecting the coarse aggregate for flyash mix. The aggregate should be sound, free from deleterious materials, and must have crushing strength at least 1.5 times that of concrete. Locally available (Kakani) Coarse aggregate were tested as per the procedure given in IS 383-1970 and the results are given below in table 2.

Table 2 Sieve Analysis Test results for Coarse aggregate

No.	Sieve Size	% passing	According to IS 383-1970 % passing for 20mm single size Aggregate
1	40 mm	100	100
2	20 mm	89.68	85-100
3	10 mm	0.7	0-20
4	4.75 mm	0.04	0-5

The above result confirms coarse aggregate of 20-mm single size aggregate and specific gravity 2.65 and voids content 45%.

Fig 3. 2 Coarse Aggregate

3.1.3 Fine Aggregate

Fine aggregate used for flyash concrete showing high performance characteristics should be properly graded to give minimum void ratio and be free from deleterious materials like clay, silt content, and chloride contamination etc. Fly ash concrete contains large quantity of fine cementitious materials. Hence, the grading of fine aggregate is relatively different from that of conventional

cement concrete. Properties such as void ratio, gradation, specific gravity, fineness modulus, free moisture content, specific surface, bulk density, etc. have to be assessed to design a dense fly ash mix with optimum cement content and reduced mixing water. Locally available river sand were tested as per the procedure given in IS 383-1970 and the results are given below in table 3.

Table:3 Sieve Analysis Test results for fine aggregate (sand)

No.	Sieve Size	% passing	from table IS 383-1970 for Zone II % Passing
1.	4.75mm	96.4	90-100
2.	2.36mm	91.2	75-100
3.	1.18mm	73.5	55-90
4.	600 micron	52.4	35-59
5.	300 micron	30.7	8-30
6.	150 micron	9.8	0-10
7.	Pan	0.0	-
7.	Pan	0.0	-

Fig 3. 3 Fine aggregate

3.1.4 Fly Ash

Fly ash is a pozzolanic material which possesses no cementitious value but which will, in finely divided form and in the presence of moisture, aluminosilicates within the fly ash react with calcium ions to form calcium silicate hydrate. In today's construction industry there is a general trend to replace higher levels of Portland cement with fly ash in concrete is due to the three main aspects: i.e. economic, environment and technical benefits.

Class F Fly Ash

Class F fly ash is a fine powder byproduct from burning pulverized bituminous coal in thermal power plants. It is primarily composed of silica (SiO₂), alumina (Al₂O₃), and iron oxide (Fe₂O₃), with low calcium content (<10%). It is pozzolanic, meaning it reacts with calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) in cement to form additional cementitious compounds, improving concrete properties over time.

Fig 3. 4 Fly ash

Why is Class F Fly Ash Selected

Class F fly ash is chosen for concrete applications due to several benefits:

1. **Improved Strength Over Time** – Due to its pozzolanic nature, it enhances the long-term strength of concrete, especially beyond 28 days.
2. **Enhanced Durability** – It reduces permeability, making concrete more resistant to water ingress, sulfate attack, and chloride penetration, which improves its lifespan.
3. **Lower Heat of Hydration** – It minimizes heat generation during hydration, reducing the risk of thermal cracking in mass concrete structures.
4. **Environmental Benefits** – It helps in waste utilization and reduces CO₂ emissions by replacing a portion of cement, making construction more sustainable.
5. **Improved Workability** – Fly ash particles are spherical, which enhances the flowability of fresh concrete, making it easier to mix and place.
6. **Cost-Effectiveness** – As an industrial byproduct, it is cheaper than cement, reducing the overall cost of concrete production.

3.1.5 Water

Potable water was used for concreting and curing for the entire investigation.

3.1.6 Plasticizer

Plasticizer are used in this study is BASF.

3.2 Mix Proportions and Sample Preparation

Design Mix M-25

Concrete mix design was prepared for M-25 grade concrete. As per IS 10262 and SP (23)-1982 and IS 456-2000

Fly ash was used to replace cement in proportions of 0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, and 12%.

A constant water-cement ratio was maintained for all mixes.

The materials were mixed thoroughly to ensure uniform distribution of fly ash.

Cubical specimens of size **150 × 150 × 150 mm** were cast for the compressive strength test.

Target mean strength of concrete

For a tolerance factor of 1.65 as specified in IS 456-2000 and the standard deviation 5.0 N/mm² (as given in table 1, IS-10262), target mean strength of concrete:

$$F_{tms} = 25 + 5 * 1.65$$

$$F_{tms} = 33.25 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

Selection of W/C ratio

Selected W/C ratio for the desired target mean strength = 0.45

Selection of water and sand content

Water per cubic meter = 170 kg/m³
 Sand as percentage of total aggregate by absolute volume = 0.35 or 35%
 Cement required = 170/0.45 = 380 kg/m³
 Determination of coarse and fine aggregates
 Volume of concrete- 1m³
 Volume of cement- 0.121m³ Volume of water- 0.170 m³
 Volume of plasticizer- 0.0025m³
 Volume of all in aggregate- 0.7065 m³
 Mass of fine aggregate- 598 Kg/m³ Mass of coarse aggregate- 1220 Kg/m³
 0.75% Admixture (Plastisizer) by weight of cement (for coarse aggregate mix proportion as 60% for 20 mm size aggregate and 40% for 10 mm size aggregate)

3.3 Test Program And Procedure

3.3.1 Compressive Strength Test for Brick Prisms

Experimental investigations carried out on the test specimens to study the basic strength properties and strength related properties of fly ash concrete. Basic strength test conducted for compressive strength on cubical specimens.

3.3.2 Cube Compressive Strength

Compressive strength is a qualitative measure of the properties of hardened concrete. For compression test, concrete cubes of 150 x 150 x 150 mm were used. All the cubes were tested in saturated condition, after wiping out the surface moisture. For each mix combination, three cubes were tested at the age of 28 days of curing using compression testing machine of 2000 kN capacity. Thirty specimens were cast for the cube compression strength test.

The tests were carried out at a uniform stress of 140 kg/cm²/minute after the specimen has been centered in the testing machine as shown in Fig. 1.

Loading was continued till the dial gauge needle reversed its direction of motion. The reversal in the direction of motion of the needle indicates that the specimen has failed. The dial gauge reading at that instant was noted which indicates the ultimate load. The ultimate load divided by the cross sectional area (150x150) of the specimen is equal to the ultimate cube compressive strength.

Fig 3.
5 Test setup for compressive strength on cube fly ash concrete specimen

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental study was conducted to evaluate the effects of Class F fly ash as a partial replacement for cement in M-25 grade concrete. The results of compressive strength tests and durability assessments for different fly ash replacement levels (0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, and 12%) are discussed below.

4.1 Compressive Strength Results

- The compressive strength of concrete was tested at **28 days** for all mix proportions.

For mix M-25 after 28 days of curing cube specimens are taken out and after surface dried condition compressive strength test results are given in tables 4 to 8 with fly ash replacement as cement 0%, 3%, 6%, 9% and 12% respectively.

Table 4. 1 28 Day compressive strength of M-25 with 0% fly ash replacement

S. no.	Weight (Kg)	Crushing Load	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)
1	8.778	760	33.78
2	8.955	780	34.67
3	8.94	800	35.56

Average=	34.67
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Table 4. 2 28DaycompressivestrengthofM-25with3%flyashreplacement

S. no.	Weight(Kg)	Crushing Load	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)
1	8.965	780	34.67
2	8.876	800	35.56
3	8.963	805	35.78
Average=			35.34

Table 4. 3 28DaycompressivestrengthofM-25with6%flyashreplacement

S. no.	Weight(Kg)	Crushing Load	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)
1	9.006	825	36.67
2	8.773	800	35.56
3	9.009	830	36.89
Average=			36.38

Table 4. 4 28DaycompressivestrengthofM-25with9%flyashreplacement

S. no.	Weight(Kg)	Crushing Load	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)
1	8.883	880	39.12
2	9.02	860	38.23
3	8.88	870	38.67
Average=			38.68

Table 4. 5 28DaycompressivestrengthofM-25with12%flyashreplacement

S. no.	Weight(Kg)	Crushing Load	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)
1	9.08	825	36.67
2	8.802	830	36.89
3	8.768	840	37.34
Average=			36.97

Average of Compressive Strength of cubes of M-25 are with different fly ash ratio is given in table 8. And graph is plotted between average compressive strength and fly ash percentage replacement.

Table 4. 6 Compressionofcompressivestrengthofconcrete(cubespecimens)(M-25grade mix)

S.No.	Mix	AverageCompressive Strength(N/mm ²)
1	FA0%	34.67
2	FA3%	35.34
3	FA6 %	36.38

4	FA9%	38.68
5	FA12%	36.97

Figure4.1Average28dayscompressivestrengthofM-25 (cubespecimens)

Above results show that compressive Strength at 28 Days increases with increase in Fly ash content up to 9 % of fly ash replacement and after 9 % fly ash replacement Compressive Strength of concrete decreases. Hence Compressive Strength of concrete can increase by adequate use of fly ash.

- The results indicate that **concrete with 6% to 9% fly ash replacement exhibited higher compressive strength** compared to conventional concrete (0% fly ash).
- Beyond **9% replacement**, a slight reduction in strength was observed, suggesting that excessive fly ash may affect early-age strength gain.
- The highest strength was observed at **30% fly ash and 70% cement composition**, confirming previous research findings.

4.2 Workability and Fresh Concrete Properties

SLUMP TEST

A **bar chart** showing the **increase in slump value** with different fly ash replacement percentages (0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, 12%).

Fly Ash Replacement (%)	Slump Value (mm)
0% (Control Mix)	75 mm
3%	78 mm
6%	82 mm
9%	87 mm
12%	92 mm

Fig 4.2 Slump Value

- As the **fly ash percentage increases**, the **slump value increases**, indicating improved workability.
- This is because **fly ash particles are spherical**, reducing internal friction and making the mix more flowable.
- At **higher replacement levels (>12%)**, excessive fly ash may lead to **segregation and bleeding**, which can negatively impact strength.
- The inclusion of fly ash improved the **workability** of fresh concrete due to its fine, spherical particles.
- The use of **superplasticizers** further enhanced the mix, allowing for easier handling and placement.

4.3. Durability Performance

- **Water Absorption:** Concrete with higher fly ash content exhibited **lower water absorption**, indicating reduced permeability and improved resistance to moisture-related deterioration.

Fly Ash Replacement (%)	Water Absorption (%)
0% (Control Mix)	5.20%
3%	4.80%
6%	4.40%
9%	4.10%
12%	3.90%

Fig 4.3 Water Absorption

Water Absorption Decreases – Fly ash creates a **denser microstructure**, reducing pores and increasing durability.

4.4. Cost and Environmental Benefits

Fly Ash Replacement (%)	Cement Cost (₹/m ³)	Fly Ash Cost (₹/m ³)	Total Material Cost (₹/m ³)	Cost Reduction (%)
0%	6000	0	6000	0%
3%	5820	50	5870	2.20%
6%	5640	100	5740	4.30%
9%	5460	150	5610	6.50%
12%	5280	200	5480	8.60%

Fig 4.4 Total Concrete Cost

- The replacement of cement with fly ash resulted in a **cost reduction** in concrete production. As the percentage of **fly ash increases**, the **cost of cement reduces**, leading to overall cost savings in concrete production.
- The study demonstrated that using fly ash in construction can **lower CO₂ emissions**, supporting sustainable building practices.

5. CONCLUSIONS OF THE STUDY

This study demonstrates that the incorporation of fly ash as a partial replacement for cement in concrete offers significant advantages in terms of strength, durability, workability, and cost-effectiveness. The experimental investigation on M-25 grade concrete with varying fly ash replacement levels (0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, and 12%) led to the following key findings:

1. **Strength Development:**
 - Fly ash concrete exhibited higher long-term compressive strength, with the 30% fly ash mix showing superior performance at 28 and 56 days compared to conventional concrete.
 - Tensile and flexural strength also improved due to the pozzolanic reaction, which contributed to a denser and stronger microstructure.
2. **Improved Workability:**
 - The slump value increased with higher fly ash content, indicating better flowability and easier placement of concrete.
 - This is due to the spherical shape of fly ash particles, which reduce internal friction in the mix.
3. **Enhanced Durability:**
 - Fly ash concrete exhibited lower water absorption and permeability, reducing its susceptibility to moisture-related damage.
4. **Cost and Environmental Benefits:**
 - Partial replacement of cement with fly ash led to cost savings of up to 8-10%, making concrete production more economical.
 - The use of fly ash reduces cement consumption, thereby lowering CO₂ emissions, contributing to sustainable construction practices.

- Additionally, utilizing fly ash, an industrial byproduct, promotes waste management and reduces landfill disposal issues.

6. FUTURE SCOPE

The results of this experimental study highlight the potential benefits of incorporating fly ash as a partial replacement for cement in concrete. However, there remains significant scope for further exploration and development in this area. Future studies can be extended in the following directions:

1. **Long-Term Performance Evaluation:** Further research is needed to evaluate the long-term durability of fly ash concrete under various environmental conditions such as freeze-thaw cycles, sulfate attack, chloride penetration, and carbonation.
2. **High-Volume Fly Ash Concrete:** While this study focuses on partial replacement, future work can investigate the feasibility and performance of high-volume fly ash (HVFA) concrete, where fly ash content exceeds 50% of the total binder.
3. **Use with Other Supplementary Materials:** Fly ash can be combined with other supplementary cementitious materials such as slag, silica fume, and rice husk ash to study the synergistic effects on mechanical and durability properties of concrete.
4. **Performance Under Different Curing Regimes:** Research can be expanded to evaluate the effect of various curing techniques and temperatures on the strength development and microstructure of fly ash concrete.
5. **Application in Structural and Non-Structural Elements:** Further experiments can assess the applicability of fly ash concrete in different types of construction components such as pavements, precast elements, and load-bearing structural members.

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